

Validating a Citizen Observatories enabling Platform by completing a Citizen Science Loop

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Abstract – Citizen Observatories (COs) are innovative mechanisms to engage citizens in monitoring and addressing environmental and societal challenges. However, their effectiveness hinges on seamless data crowdsourcing, high-quality data analysis, and impactful data-driven decision-making. This paper validates how the GREENGAGE project enables and encourages the accomplishment of the Citizen Science Loop within COs, showcasing how its digital infrastructure and knowledge assets facilitate the co-production of thematic co-explorations. By systematically structuring the Citizen Science Loop—from problem identification to impact assessment—we demonstrate how GREENGAGE enhances data collection, analysis, and evidence exposition. For that, this paper illustrates how the GREENGAGE approach and associated technologies have been successfully applied at a university campus to conduct an air quality and public space suitability thematic co-exploration.

Keywords — Citizen Observatory, thematic co-exploration, co-production, data analysis, Green Deal

I. INTRODUCTION

Citizen Observatories (COs) empower individuals to actively participate in data collection and environmental monitoring to address local challenges. The GREENGAGE project, under the Horizon Europe framework, aims to enhance the efficacy and more widespread adoption of COs by providing a structured Citizen Science Loop methodology operationalized by a co-production process [1] which is enabled by its GREEN Engine infrastructure[2]. One core contribution brought forward by GREENGAGE is the “thematic co-exploration” concept. A thematic co-exploration, in the context of COs, refers to a collaborative approach where citizens actively participate alongside scientists and other stakeholders in exploring specific themes or topics related to environmental monitoring and observation. Through them, COs are made purposeful by leveraging the collective efforts of individuals, often non-scientists, to gather, share, and analyse environmental data, typically facilitated by digital tools and technologies.

This paper describes the validation of the GREENGAGE co-creation process for thematic co-explorations, through a university campus based thematic co-exploration, which results in the execution of the following 6 steps (see Fig. 1) of a Citizen Science loop, namely: a) *problem identification* – recognizing research questions or societal challenges suitable

for public engagement; b) *campaign design* – developing participatory protocols, data collection methodologies, and toolkits for citizens’ engagement; c) *data crowdsourcing* – enabling citizen scientists to gather good quality observations via digital applications, sensors, and surveys, through data crowdsourcing activities; d) *data analysis & interpretation* – employing AI-driven tools for insight extraction and thus making humanly meaningful the data modelled; e) *feedback & collective learning* – validating findings with humans and providing participants with actionable feedback; and f) *action & impact* - informing policies, creating solutions, and refining methodologies for future CS campaigns exploring similar or complementary thematic co-explorations.

Fig. 1. Citizen Science’ loop in thematic co-explorations.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Firstly, a state of the art on methodologies and tools to streamline and make feasible the accomplishment of CS loop is given. Secondly, the GREENGAGE platform is described. Thirdly, the stages carried out within GREENGAGE project to validate the provided infrastructure in a real use case are detailed. Fourthly, the evaluation of the scenario considered and some reflections around it are raised. Finally, the paper concludes with some conclusions and further work proposals.

II. RELATED WORK

Citizen Observatories (COs) have emerged as powerful tools for engaging the public in environmental monitoring and scientific research. However, organizing and sustaining these initiatives has presented significant challenges. Several past projects have attempted to address these difficulties, focusing on various aspects of CO implementation and management. The WeObserve project [3] aimed to create a sustainable ecosystem of COs by developing communities of practice and addressing key challenges such as data quality, citizen engagement, and impact assessment. Similarly, the GROW Observatory project [4] focused on soil moisture monitoring, emphasizing the importance of tailored technology and community-driven research to align with broader sustainability goals. Other notable initiatives include the Ground Truth 2.0 project [5], which developed and implemented six citizen observatories in real conditions across Europe and Africa. This project focused on creating a multi-stakeholder platform that combined scientific, citizen-collected, and authoritative data to inform decision-making processes. The LandSense project [6], on the other hand, built a citizen observatory for land-use and land-cover monitoring, leveraging advanced earth observation techniques and mobile technology to engage citizens in environmental monitoring. These projects have made significant strides in mobilizing citizen engagement and demonstrating the potential of citizen science in addressing environmental challenges.

The GREENGAGE project, however, takes a more comprehensive approach to enabling and sustaining COs. Unlike previous initiatives, GREENGAGE provides a structured Citizen Science Loop methodology operationalized by a co-production process and supported by its GREEN Engine infrastructure. This approach encompasses the entire lifecycle of CO's thematic co-explorations, from problem identification to impact assessment, addressing key challenges such as data quality, participant retention, and policy integration. The project's suite of tools and knowledge assets, including its Collaborative Environment tool [7] and thematic co-exploration specification templates [8], offer a more holistic solution for CO management and execution. By providing a flexible, adaptable framework and a rich set of resources through its Academy [9], GREENGAGE has the potential to further democratize citizen science and enhance the effectiveness of COs in influencing policy-making and addressing environmental challenges. The project's emphasis on thematic co-explorations allows for focused, community-driven research that aligns with broader sustainability goals. Additionally, its GREEN Engine infrastructure provides a more integrated platform for data collection, analysis, and visualization compared to previous projects, potentially addressing the challenges of data quality and reliability that have been persistent in citizen science initiatives.

III. GREENGAGE PLATFORM TO ENABLE CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

These CS loop stages shown in Fig. 1 are aligned to the main phases established by GREENGAGE's co-creation process for thematic co-explorations, which has been devised to organize, execute and exploit the results of CS campaigns. These main phases which compose the GREENGAGE co-creation process, supported by the Collaborative Environment (see Fig. 2), are:

- *Phase 1 - preparing*: fully aligned with the “problem identification” stage of a Citizen Science loop, comprises the following aspects: a) theme selection; b) pilot owners training; c) core team onboarding and d) core team training.
- *Phase 2 – designing*: aligned with the “campaign design” stage of a CS loop, comprising: a) experiment specification; b) tools’ resources selection; c) tools resources customization and d) tools resources testing.
- *Phase 3 – experimenting*: aligned with both the “data crowdsourcing” and “data analysis & interpretation” steps of a CS loop. It comprises the following activities: observers onboarding, observers training support, data collection, data combination, data analysis, data visualization and evaluation.
- *Phase 4 – sharing*: aligned with “feedback & learning” and “action & impact” stages of CS loop, comprising the following tasks defined in the GREENGAGE thematic co-exploration process, namely storytelling, policy advocacy and sustainability.

Fig. 2. Sample co-production process for AQ thematic co-exploration.

Fig. 3. Citizen Observers' journey proposed by GREENGAGE [1].

Each phase is supported by GREENGAGE's GREEN Engine infrastructure, which integrates various digital tools and knowledge assets to streamline the co-production process. As was already described at [1], the tools and knowledge assets created in GREENGAGE are categorized in the following areas of concern, as shown in Fig. 3, where the names of the tools defined for each layer is indicated:

1. *Community and Co-production Process Management*: In it, the emphasis is on building a strong, informed, and active community which collaborates through a co-production process by defining a hypothesis, research questions formulation or datasets selection, among others.
2. *Data Crowdsourcing and Capture*: Based on the groundwork of the previous area of concern, this materialises into concrete data collection activities. It is characterized by active participation, leveraging technology to gather vital curated high quality environmental data.
3. *Data Analysis and Insights Generation*: In this latter area of concern, the collected data is transformed into actionable insights. This is where the data, once transformed in actionable information, becomes a powerful tool for understanding and influencing environmental policy.

The purpose of this work is to exemplify how the CS loop is enabled through the suite of tools and knowledge assets defined by GREENGAGE and shown in Fig. 3. Thus, next section describes how GREENGAGE validates the Citizen Science Loop through a real-world thematic co-exploration at the University of Deusto.

IV. CITIZEN SCIENCE LOOP STEP-WISED CO-CREATION

This section showcases the process, tools and results obtained when applying the GREENGAGE CO-enabling approach to a real use-case, namely, “*reflection on the suitability and air quality of important points of interest (POIs) within the campus of the University of Deusto in Bilbao, Spain*”. The following subsections describe the different steps completed towards fulfilling the CS loop for this thematic co-exploration, guided by the process depicted at Fig. 1. Notice that to coordinate the execution of this co-creation process, a new process was defined in the Collaborative Environment as shown in Fig. 2.

A. CS campaign specification

First thing in the organization of a thematic co-exploration, within a Citizen Observatory, is to decide what is the socio-economic and/or environmental challenge that wants to be addressed. There are different aspects that need to be decided at this stage. A useful knowledge asset or CO enabler, as they are called in GREENGAGE, is the *thematic co-exploration specification template* which is a Word template which guides the organizers of a thematic co-exploration through the following questions: a) *WHY* – reason why this Citizen Observatory’ thematic co-exploration is needed; b) *WHO* – stakeholders involved and affected who need to be recruited for the co-exploration to take place and for the outcomes to be disseminated to; c) *WHAT* – actual endeavours/activities of the Citizen Observatory’s thematic co-exploration towards validating a defined hypothesis and populate a given set of metrics; d) *WHEN* – planning of activities (resources&time) when undertaking the Citizen Observatory’s thematic co-exploration, e.g. crowd-sourcing and data analysis sessions needed; e) *WHERE* – geographical area where Citizen Observatory’s thematic co-exploration will take place, i.e. area to cover and specific points and frequency of measurements which are needed to ensure valuable crowdsourced data; f) *WHICH* – materials and resources, i.e. actual materials, devices and tools needed to execute the

Citizen Observatory’s thematic co-exploration, coming either from GREENGAGE or other publicly available tools and assets; g) *HOW* – specification of data analysis processes/workflows to be able to capture, analyse and generate indicators and visualizations sought in Citizen Observatory’s thematic co-exploration. In this stage the needed visualizations and possible storytelling approaches to be eventually adopted are co-specified too.

As result, in this stage, applied to our exemplary thematic co-exploration, the following decisions were taken:

- *Set up the observers’ team*, in this case 10 researchers associated to the MORElab research group were recruited and committed to be engaged in the whole co-creation process.
- *Definition of different places (POIs)* at the University’s campus (4 were selected) where to gather air quality and place suitability perceptions. These POIs are in the surroundings of the Faculty of Engineering’s building at University of Deusto.
- *Definition of metrics* to estimate air quality and campus space suitability. For that, two new metrics were co-defined by the team of observers in a meeting, namely, a *Perception of Air Quality Index (PAQI)* was made up, where on a scale from 1 to 5, people have to indicate their perception from very clean (no noticeable pollution effects) to highly polluted (major health concerns, unlivable conditions), and, the *Public Space Suitability Index (PSSI)* was also made up, where again in a 1 to 5 scale, volunteers have to express their perception regarding accessibility & connectivity (20%), safety & security (15%), environmental quality (15%), functionality & comfort (20%), sociability & inclusivity (15%) or maintenance & management (15%) aspects. Again, 5 ranges of suitability were defined ranging from excellent suitability (average answer values >4) to poor suitability (<1). Apart from perceptions of air quality, those volunteers who counted with an Atmotube Pro[10] device also collected air quality data through it.
- *Definition of tasks* to be performed at each selected POI. Firstly, gather a visual perception (photo) and secondly, complete a short 3 question survey for volunteers to express their perception about place suitability and air quality, plus having the chance to leave some feedback about the visited POI. Notice that for the sake of simplicity, one single question per metric was provided to feed the above-mentioned metrics. In a more extensive and thorough real-world thematic co-exploration, one question for each of the factors feeding the devised PSSI should have been included, for instance.

B. Design of a crowdsourcing campaign

Once the specification of the thematic co-exploration is ready, the next critical stage is to *co-design the CS crowdsourcing campaign* – based on the hypothesis, objectives and data gaps previously identified. In GREENGAGE, the following parameters must be completed in order to set up a CS crowdsourcing campaign: a) a new instance of an *observatory* entity is defined, specifying a name for it and the geographical area it covers; b) a *set of POIs* within the defined area are defined, for each POI the following fields are defined: type (e.g. culture, nature and so on), description, latitude & longitude, and optional photo; c) in

each POI *several tasks* can be defined, usually in a campaign the same tasks are required at every measurement point, for each task the following fields are defined: POI associated, topic (e.g. air quality, safety and so on), type (survey, photo, walk and so on), title, description and geocoordinates; e) for tasks of type survey, a survey has been created or an already existing one linked, providing the following fields: title and a set of questions, where for each question a title, type (single choice, multiple choice, text request), and options as pairs of id and values must be defined. Fig. 4 exemplifies the crowdsourcing campaign defined for the thematic co-exploration at Deusto's campus.

Entity	Field1	Field2
observatory1	title	University of Deusto's campus
	area	[lat1, lon1, lat2, lon2]
POI1	type	air quality
	description	entrance to Faculty of Engineering
	latitude&longitude	43,2708236, -2,9402889
	tasks	[task1, task2]
task1	POI	POI1
	topic	suitability
	type	SURVEY
	survey	survey1
task2	POI	POI1
	topic	air quality
	type	PHOTO
survey1	title	
	questions	[question1, question2, question3]
question1	title	What is the perceived air quality?
	type	SINGLE_CHOICE
	option1	very clean
	option2	clean
	option3	normal
	option4	polluted
option5	highly polluted	
question2		
...	type	SINGLE_CHOICE
question 3		
...	type	TEXT

Fig. 4. Specification of crowdsourcing campaign.

C. Collect, extract, transform and load campaign data

Once the campaign had been specified, on Friday 14th March 2025, from 11:30am to 12:30pm CET, a crowdsourcing campaign was executed, where 10 people took part. The GREENGAGE app, as shown in Fig. 5, was used to collect data:

Fig. 5. GREENGAGE app used for data crowdsourcing.

The crowdsourcing campaign data was collected through an ETL process. Whilst, the PRE and POST impact and satisfaction questionnaires were hosted in Google Forms, the the GREENGAGE app's collected data was hosted at Apollo Server which exhibits a GraphQL API. This API allows clients (such as mobile apps or web frontends) to efficiently query and interact with campaign data. This interface was used to retrieve all data crowdsourced associated to the POIs and spots generated in the thematic co-exploration's crowdsourcing campaign. Fig. 6 shows the Apollo Server front-end where details in JSON about tasks performed in the crowdsourcing campaign are retrieved by means of a GraphQL query. Notice that GraphQL is a modern API query language and runtime that allows clients to request precisely the data they need in a single request, unlike RESTful APIs which rely on multiple endpoints and fixed data structures, often leading to over-fetching or under-fetching of data.

Fig. 6. Front-end of Apollo Server where GraphQL queries are issued.

The ETL process corresponding to the crowdsourcing campaign was implemented as a Python script utilizing asynchronous programming patterns to efficiently extract, transform, and load GREENGAGE app's data. For data extraction, the script interfaces with GREENGAGE app's GraphQL API endpoint to retrieve mission data, including various mission types (e.g. SURVEY, WALK or DATASET). Additional observatory-related data is collected to provide geographical context for each mission during transform stage of the process. Finally, the script also interfaces with a Keycloak-based [11] authentication service customized for GREENGAGE, which allows extracting participants' socioeconomic user data. Such service enables anonymization while preserving demographic information. Fig. 7 illustrates the web form devised that was completed by the 10 volunteers of the campaign to have access to GREENGAGE resources.

During transformation, mission data is processed according to type-specific rules. For example, a SURVEY type task, requires additional API calls to retrieve associated quantitative survey values, or GEOTRACKING type mission requires additional API call to retrieve associated GeoJSON object. The transformation phase maps tasks to observatory information, enriches records with anonymized user demographic data, and converts all data to a standardized CSV format with appropriate fields for analysis. This step is crucial because Apache Druid [12], the real-time analytics database used in the loading phase, requires data to be ingested in a structured format. Druid stores data internally in a columnar format, which optimizes it for fast aggregations and queries.

Finally, the load phase utilizes Apache Druid's ingestion API [13] to load the transformed data. The script generates a comprehensive ingestion specification defining data types,

dimensions, and granularity settings to optimize subsequent analytical queries. Once ingested, the data becomes immediately queryable through Druid's SQL API, which enables seamless integration with visualization platforms like Apache Superset and other analytics tools.

Notice that 3 ETL processes were set up to extract, transform and load data from: 1) photos gathered through task 2 (see Fig. 4); 2) survey answers associated to the different users and POIs where surveys were responded through task 1 (see Fig. 4); and c) socio demographic data completed by volunteers when they signed up to take part in the observatory, by means of the <https://me.greengage-project.eu> page shown at Fig. 7. As result of these ETL processes, data was stored in Apache Druid infrastructure (see Fig. 8), which is the storage solution chosen within GREEN Engine.

Welcome to GREENGAGE!

Please answer a few questions about yourself below. This type of information is known in research terms as collecting sociodemographic (which in basic terms means: the study of human data. We need these answers so as to better understand who are becoming Citizen Observers and engaging with our project. We are collecting this data and further process the information anonymously) around categories or groupings, to do with individuals' backgrounds (known as 'socio-economic and demographic' data). Our project is committed to values around social inclusion, including everyone of all walks of life and experience. As such, we need to know that we are involving as many different types of people as possible in GREENGAGE-supported Citizen Observatories. This is known as aggregated data (raw data such as your level of formal education) which can be summarized so as to make sure we include, for example, a variety of age groups, work backgrounds and genders. The 'Terms of use' at the bottom of the page explain how carefully we manage your personal data and our Data Privacy Information provides you with all data protection relevant information.

In what role do you play within GREENGAGE in ideas and concepts, known as thematic co-explorations?

- Participant - active participant in a thematic co-exploration team
- Core team member - organizer and knowledge leader of a thematic co-exploration
- Pilot owner - promoter of a thematic co-exploration in a domain
- Citizenry - target for sharing (dissemination) the communication of results of a thematic co-exploration
- Stakeholder - sponsor and receiver of results of a thematic co-exploration

Please, select your pilot site or indicate your location, e.g. name of your place or ZIP code

Other:

Gender:

What is your level of education?

What is your level of knowledge in the usage of digital tools?

Could you indicate your work status?

Please, select the type of organization you represent:

Do you consider yourself to belong to a minority or socially disadvantaged group based around, for example, ethnicity, gender, economic or social background, or other?

What is your age?

I consent to taking part in the GREENGAGE research project based on the [privacy policy](#)

Fig. 7. Sociodemographic profile of campaign participants.

As result of such campaign the following number of measurements were gathered:

- 10 people completed a sociodemographic questionnaire which granted them access GREENGAGE app, after a consent form was signed.
- 10 people also completed the PRE Impact evaluation questionnaire, as part of the ex-ante and ex-post evaluation approach [14] adopted by the project.

- 10 people completed an alpha testing questionnaire to provide feedback about the GREENGAGE app, and thus enhance its eventual acceptance.
- 10 people completed the POST Impact evaluation questionnaire
- 21 photos were gathered at spots defined near the 4 POIs visited by the 10 volunteers, where potential issues were identified.
- 90 answers to the 3-question survey associated to each of the 4 POIs defined in the campaign were gathered.
- 180 air quality measurements were gathered by the 4 Atmotube devices carried by volunteers (39 PM2.5 measurements).

ID	Date	POI	Survey Response
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-001	Very good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-002	Good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-003	Very good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-004	Good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-005	Very good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-006	Good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-007	Very good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-008	Good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-009	Very good
2023-08-17 11:30:00	2023-08-17 11:30	GreenGage-010	Good

Fig. 8. Crowdsourcing campaign's survey data loaded into Druid.

Fig. 9. Geolocated survey's analysis for one single POI.

Fig. 10. Geolocated survey's analysis for one question in all POIs.

D. Analyse data through visualisations & reflection

Once data had been collected into Druid, helped by Apache Superset tool [15] a range of visualizations was created. Fig. 9 shows the dashboard created with this tool which analyses answers to the question "How do you rate air

quality at POI4?”. In the top left-hand side in a pie chart we notice that volunteers’ perception was good or very good in 70% of the cases, i.e. for 7 out of the 10 volunteers that took part. The table below the pie chart shows the answers’ distribution out of the 4 categories, there are 5 (no answer for “bad” was received). Interestingly, the PM2.5 concentration gathered by the 4 volunteers that also carried out an Atmotube device whilst they went around with the GREENGAGE app is shown at the bottom right side. During the crowdsourcing campaign’s time, the concentration of PM2.5 was in the range 1 to 7.8. Most studies [16] indicate PM2.5 at or below 12 µg/m3 is considered healthy with little to no risk from exposure. If the level goes to or above 35 µg/m3 during a 24-hour period, the air is considered unhealthy and can cause issues for people with existing breathing issues such as asthma. Hence, users’ perceptions regarding air quality match what the Atmotube devices reflected in their measurements.

Additionally, results from all questions and all POIs were aggregated in other charts. For instance, Fig. 10 depicts that in above 55% of the cases, volunteers considered that the air quality at the 4 POIs selected was good or very good.

E. Evaluation of the thematic co-exploration experience and results

Analysing the data visualized in the Superset has allowed us to draw some few conclusions. There has been alignment between the perceptions regarding air quality and the actual measurements obtained through more reliable devices as Atmotube. This fact was reflected per POI, see Fig. 9 for POI4 and Fig. 10 which aggregates the air quality perceptions in all POIs. Similarly, info about the suitability of the different places was gathered and analysed at each POI and for the whole campus, taking the average value of the PSSI in the 4 points that represent the campus. Finally, some feedback was gathered from those visiting the POIs, who mainly took some pictures in spots, i.e. locations, close to the POIs where they found something remarkable regarding the suitability or the air quality of the place. Fig. 11 shows an HTML visualization generated with all the spots collected.

Fig. 11. Ad-hoc HTML visualization with spots in Deusto’s campaign.

Analysing the spots and the comments received in question 3 of survey 1 (see Fig. 4), it was found that although generally the status of the campus is considered quite adequate, issues related to the fact that pedestrians and cars often share common spaces, it might be troublesome. Fig. 12

summarizes the sociodemographic profile of participants in the campaign, where 3 women and 7 men, owning 5 iPhones and 6 Android devices, half of them not associated to GREENGAGE took part. Notice that the predominant age range was 25-50 years, and they were digitally literate participants with master or PhD studies.

F. Feedback and action: Social media dissemination, policymaking, replication

To close the CS loop and contribute towards the positive transformation of Deusto’s campus in Bilbao, the following actions were taken:

1. *Discourse theme* was created through which participants could communicate with each other. Results were announced through this Discourse [17] channel and participants had the opportunity to comment on the generated visualizations and in the interpretations performed by all of them.
2. *X and LinkedIn social media channels* were used to summarize the thematic co-exploration completed main conclusions.
3. *A policy brief* was created and sent to the vice-chancellor in the university of Deusto responsible for the campus refurbishment.
4. *Impact analysis* about the executed campaign in terms of social, political and citizen science aspects was performed, following the ACTION project’s [18] impact evaluation approach.

Fig. 12. Sociodemographic data analysis.

V. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

The paper has demonstrated how GREENGAGE infrastructure and suite of enablers configuring its Academy successfully bridge the gap between citizen participation and environmental decision-making. The completion of a whole Citizen Science Loop for the campus in Bilbao of the University of Deusto has been demonstrated. 10 participants with high digital acquaintances took part and made use of a wide range of tools and CO enablers, namely, Collaborative Environment, Discourse, Apollo server, Apache Druid and Apache Superset, together with enablers such as the “thematic co-exploration specification” or the “policy brief template”.

The main insight is that laypeople, after brief training, can follow the right protocol to gather good enough data to perform effective analysis or, at least, reflect on the results of

data analysis' visualizations. However, in the interviews carried out to participants after taking part in the campaign, they acknowledged that the generation of visualization with Superset or the aggregation and curation of data through ETL processes is complex, requires programming and data analysis skills. Still, interpretation of charts can be made accessible when some more expert people explain and discuss results with volunteers. Hence, continuous guidance and support for volunteers in CS observatories is critical to maintaining their interest across the whole thematic co-exploration's duration. Besides, several feedback loops are necessary to keep the community tuned after each of the steps necessary to complete the CS loop, e.g. through a Discourse channel. A core aspect of every thematic co-exploration is the collaborative (co-design & co-creation) activities that participants take part in. For this use case, the following sessions were realized: a) initial training, specification of the thematic co-exploration, team and co-creation process setup; b) crowdsourcing campaign and co-design of possible useful visualizations; c) collaborative reflection on the gathered data and analysis results; d) participation in Discourse channel, social media dissemination of public results and policy brief.

Future work will work will complete this validation with the publication of the datasets generated in Zenodo[19], and with the completion of the impact analysis following ACTION project's guidelines. Besides, an optimized gamified app for crowdsourcing which enables further constraints to be assigned to campaigns, is in the pipeline. More sophisticated visualization technologies beyond the functional Superset will also be considered such as Kepler or ad-hoc HTML Charts.js visualizations. Finally, future work will further assess the scalability and adaptability of GREENGAGE in diverse environmental contexts. As a matter of fact, currently the GREENGAGE approach and technology is being piloted in four pan-European pilots, where different societal groups intervene in those Citizen Observatories.

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